

INFLUENCE OF UZBEK DIALECTS ON PRONUNCIATION OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11087978>

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada o'zbek shevalarining ingliz tili talaffuziga ta'siri, tovush tizimidagi farq va o'xshashliklar, talaffuzdagi qiyinchiliklar o'rganilib, yechimlari keltirilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *interferensiya, tovush tizimi, tutuq belgisi, undosh, unli, tovush*

Abstract. *In this article, the impact of Uzbek dialects on English pronunciation, differences and similarities in the sound system, pronunciation difficulties are studied and solutions are presented.*

Keywords: *Interference, sound system, apostrophe, consonant, vowel*

Аннотация. *В данной статье изучено влияние узбекских диалектов на английское произношение, различия и сходства звуковой системы, трудности произношения и представлены пути решения.*

Ключевые слова: *интерференция, звуковая система, апостроф, согласная, гласная*

Introduction

The pronunciation problem of foreign language learners has become an even bigger problem that has been difficult to solve in recent years. For this reason, a few years ago, it was limited to knowing English grammar, but now the effort is focused on learning foreign languages. because of the movements, the language learner class has evolved so rapidly. Today, the pronunciation part of a foreign language, not the vocabulary part or the grammar part, has become the point to be conquered. It has become a priority to speak the local English language in a beautiful pronunciation, not to speak correctly. In this field, Uzbek dialects are being targeted as those who have a negative taste for beautiful pronunciation. Because the foreign language is studied in an artificial environment, the influence of dialects on the pronunciation of a foreign language is clearly felt. In this regard, approximation or interference and the differences in the sound system of both languages are the main themes of this article.

Methodology

Phonetics is the beauty of foreign language knowledge and skills. Any acquired knowledge shows its appearance only with correct and fluent pronunciation. In this regard, the question arises as to what kind of field and what kind of object, purpose and aspects phonetics has. The object of phonetics is the sound side of the language, phonetic construction. The sound side of the language includes units such as speech sounds, syllables, accent, tone (intonation, melody). The purpose of phonetics is to study the physical-acoustic, anatomical-physiological and linguistic-functional bases of phonetic units, to determine their role in language. Such a goal determines its following tasks: a) to study the laws of formation of units, such as sound, accent, melody; b) to familiarize students with the above laws and scientific and theoretical ideas related to these laws; d) identifying controversial issues related to the phonetic-phonological system, reacting to them; e) formation of phonetic analysis skills among students; f) to give students brief information about phonetists-phonologists who worked in this field. [H. Jamolkhanov. 2005, page 18]

Language is one of our spiritual values that reflects our identity, and it forms the spirit of the nation. Dialects are local forms of the language, the study of which has a theoretical meaning

from the point of view of science, and a practical meaning for the future teacher of a foreign language. The main goal of studying dialects is to reform their main elements, i.e. phonetic, lexical, morphological, and syntactic aspects. The science dealing with linguistics is called "dialectology". While thinking about this, we come across some concepts, such as dialect, dialect, and so on. So what practical meaning do they actually have for linguists? Dialect means Persian "manner", "style" and means a part of the national (people's) language related to a small territory, which is distinguished by its own lexical, phonetic and grammatical features. In order for the student's speech to be understandable, it is necessary to learn not only the pronunciation of meaningful sounds (phonemes), but also the main tone (stress, weight, pause) of simple and compound sentences that are widely used, melody) should also be mastered. So, the pronunciation skill consists of the operations of articulation (saying) and intonation (use of speech tone). [J. Jalolov. 2012, page 196].

1. Karluk dialect. This dialect is divided into 7 types: 1. Samarkand-Bukhara, 2. Tashkent. 3. Margilan-Kokand. 4. Andijan-Shahrikhan. 4-Chortaq or umlaut dialects. 5. Kokand, Andijan, Norin rural dialects with synharmonic language. 6. Northern Uzbek city (Shymkent, Turkestan) dialects. 7. Northern Uzbek rural (Mankent) dialects.

2. Oguz dialect. It includes 2 types of dialects: 1. Southern Khorezm (Khiva, Yangi Urganch, Shavot, Ghazavot, Khazorasp, Yangiariq) dialects. 2. Dialects of the Northern Oghuz group (Ikon, Karabulok).

3. Kipchak dialect. It is divided into several types: 1. Khorezm Kipchak dialects: a) Northern Khorezm ("dj" speaker); b) Middle Khorezm ("ft" dialects). 2. Composite dialects. 3. Kazakh-Naiman, Ferghana- Karakalpak dialects. 4. Northern Uzbek Kipchak dialect (Sozoq, Cholakurgan).

Results

So, what are the difficulties that learners may face in this regard, and what solutions should we find to overcome them? In the science of foreign language methodology, the types of pronunciation difficulties are classified as follows: 1. Articulatory difficulty that occurs in the individual pronunciation of a sound. 2. If two sounds (or combinations of sounds that cause alternative associations with each other) are confused (for example, long and short, voiced and unvoiced), then an oppositional difficulty occurs. 3. When the sounds are at the beginning (anlaut), in the middle (inlaut) and at the end (auslaut) of the word, or when they are adjacent to each other, there is a certain difficulty of pronunciation - positional difficulties. For example, consonants at the end and beginning of words (two or more side by side) are extremely difficult for Uzbek students. 4. Difficulties in differentiating sounds occur during hearing perception, they are called acoustic difficulties (J. Jalolov. 1996, p. 78).

Analysis

If we pay attention to the parts of the pronunciation itself, we will see that it is made up of several parts. Pronunciation consists of three parts: hearing (acoustic), speaking (motor) and expressing meaning (semantic). Each language has its own performance feature. Mastering the phonetic aspect of the language, i.e. mastering the pronunciation skill, is one of the important conditions of speech communication. The question arises whether it is possible to achieve perfect pronunciation in a foreign language in educational conditions. The Methodist answer is clear: learners learn approximate pronunciation in a foreign language (correct pronunciation can be learned in the mother tongue and in the second language). According to the idea of approximation, on the one hand, it is allowed to limit the volume of phonetic material and, on the other hand, the

quality of the pronunciation of some sounds is lower than that of the native speaker. It is known that the sound of a certain foreign language causes a change in meaning, i.e. plays a phonemic role, so it is recommended to achieve a high level of approximate approximation (approximation) in its pronunciation, for example, English the shortness and longness of the vowel sound in the language, it is necessary to strive for high approximation in the voiced-unvoiced consonant sound at the end of the word, otherwise the content will be damaged. secondly, pronunciation is complex compared to lexis and grammar, if it is determined by the artificial environment. Interference and transfer phenomena occur in foreign language learners due to these similarities and differences. This is a big enterprise. One of the scientific-practical problems in linguistics is the problem of reaction to the phenomenon of interference. In psycholinguistics, interference is associated with the process of transposition/facilitation, and in linguomethodology, it is an associative connection with difficulty and error processes (J. Jalolov, 1996, p. 123).

Discussion

From the above points, it can be concluded that pronunciation difficulties are not considered as a separate problem or a separate year is not spent to eliminate pronunciation difficulties, but it finds its solutions together with the learning stages of vocabulary and grammar. G. Palmer developed an oral course of foreign language teaching, using it in practice showed, wrote manuals. He developed the right method. His method is divided into the following stages.1) Prescriptive exercise. Pupils learn only by listening to his speech. a) The teacher pronounces, the student listens. b) Conscious understanding, the teacher gives various tasks, the student performs them. v) Performs tasks in a foreign language by command. g) Yes and No exercise, asks a general question, students answer with Yes and No.2. Prescriptive (imitation exercise). The teacher speaks, the students speak examples: a) sound, words; b) then analyze simple sentences they return3. Conversation under certain conditions. Students learn to answer questions.4. A conversation between a teacher and a student under normal circumstances.

Oral speech was both the goal and the means of teaching and learning. Therefore, if the difficulties encountered in teaching pronunciation are not eliminated in time, the language of students may become stiff and they may always pronounce these words incorrectly. In this process, it is recommended to use the audio-lingual method to achieve quick results. Because, through the audio-lingual method, it will be possible to quickly and effectively teach a foreign language to those working in hotels, shops, ports, airports, and restaurants. Based on the information studied above, the most effective way to eliminate the influence of dialects on the pronunciation of a foreign language is to listen to more listening materials. then the learner will imitate and develop pronunciation skills just like in audio material.

REFERENCES

1. Abduazizov A.A. Theoretical Phonetics of Modern English, Tashkent, 1986.
2. Abduazizov.A.A. English Phonetics. Toshkent, 2007, p 256.
3. Ashurboyev.S. O'zbek dialektologiyasi.Toshkent,2016.
4. Dickushina O.I. English Phonetics> A Theoretical Course. Moscow -Leningrad, 1965, Chapter XI.
5. English Phonetics. A Theoretical Course: Учеб Т 33 для студ. ин- товифак. иностряз./ М.А. Соколова, К.П. Гинтовт, Р.М. Тихонова. – М.: Высш. Шк., 1991- 204 с.
6. Iriskulov M.T. English phonetics, Tashkent 2007, p. 221.

7. Ismailova B.Y. O'zbek auditoriyasida birinchi kurs studentlarini ingliz tilining konsonantizmiga o'rgatishning lingvodidaktik asoslari, Toshkent, 2015.
8. Jalolov J.J. Chet til o'qitish metodikasi, Toshkent, 2012.
9. Jamolxonov H. Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili, Toshkent, 2015.
10. John Soars and Liz, New Headway, Oxford, University Press, 2006.
11. Olloyorov Q. O'zbek dialektologiyasi. Urganch, 2017.
12. Toshmatova D. Chet tili o'qitishda ona tili interferensiyasi va uni bartaraf etish usullari, Namangan, 2019.